

Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor Arising from a Dentigerous Cyst Associated with an Impacted Mandibular Lateral Incisor: A Rare Case Report and Mini-Review

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ABSTRACT - Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor (AOT) is a rare benign neoplasm of odontogenic epithelial origin that frequently mimics developmental cysts in its clinical presentation and radiographic features. Characterised by slow growth and non-invasive behaviour, this lesion shows a clear predilection for the anterior maxilla, most often in association with an unerupted canine. Mandibular involvement, particularly around a lateral incisor, is distinctly uncommon, while documented cases of AOT arising through transformation of a dentigerous cyst lining remain exceptionally uncommon in the literature.

We present a rare case of a 17-year-old female who reported with a swelling in the anterior mandible. Radiographic evaluation revealed a well-defined unilocular radiolucency surrounding the crown of an impacted mandibular lateral incisor, strongly suggestive of a dentigerous cyst but after histopathological examination, which unexpectedly demonstrated features of Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor, indicating focal transformation within the cyst lining.

This case highlights the diagnostic challenges associated with pericoronal radiolucency and emphasizes the importance of routine histopathological examination of all enucleated specimens. A brief review of previously reported cases is also presented.

Keywords - Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor, Dentigerous cyst, Hybrid odontogenic lesion, Mandibular lateral incisor

I. INTRODUCTION

Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor (AOT) is an uncommon, benign epithelial lesion of odontogenic origin, which accounts for 2.2% - 13% of all the odontogenic tumors.^[1] Till date, various authors have given multiple terminologies for this neoplasm. It was first described by Steensland et al. in 1905 as “epithelioma adamantium.”^[2] In the year 1907, **Dreibladt et al.** used the term “pseudoadenameloblastoma” for it.^[3] Philipsen and Birn proposed the name AOT, which was widely accepted and adopted by the World Health Organization classification of odontogenic tumors in 1971. AOT appears in three clinicopathologic variants: follicular, extrafollicular and peripheral. The follicular type is associated with an unerupted tooth whereas extrafollicular type has no relation with an impacted tooth and the peripheral variant is attached to the gingival structures. All AOT variants demonstrate identical histology which indicates a common derivation. It is hypothesised that the lesion originates from reduced enamel epithelium, enamel organ epithelium and cell rests of Malassez.^[4]

The follicular variant of AOT, which is commonly associated with an impacted canine (40% cases), is confused for a Dentigerous Cyst (DC) clinically and radiologically, though AOT itself is a cystic tumour in many cases. There are case reports of AOT associated with various other cysts and neoplasms such as COC, DC, ameloblastomas, odontomes.^[5] It is also known as ‘two thirds tumor,’ because 2/3rd of cases occurs in the maxilla, 2/3rd occur in young females, 2/3rd of the cases are associated with un-erupted teeth, and 2/3rd of the affected teeth are canines.^[1]

Despite its characteristic clinical profile, AOT may occasionally present in uncommon sites and in association with teeth other than the maxillary canine. However, these cases rarely reported in the literature. The present case report describes an unusual presentation of Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor associated with a mandibular lateral incisor, mimicking a dentigerous cyst.

II. CASE REPORT

A 17-year-old female patient presented with a swelling in the lower chin region of six months duration. The patient was apparently asymptomatic before the onset of the swelling, which developed spontaneously in the chin and mandibular anterior region. Initially smaller in size (bead-like) then gradually increased. The patient reported a history of dull, intermittent pain in the region one month prior to presentation, which was aggravated during chewing and subsided spontaneously without radiation. The patient had previously visited a private clinic and received medication, the details of which were not recalled, but the swelling did not resolve. At present, the swelling was painless and was not associated with bleeding or pus discharge. There was no history of trauma. The patient's medical and surgical histories were non-contributory, with no history of systemic illnesses, drug allergies, or blood transfusion.

On extraoral examination, no abnormality detected with skin, eyes and TMJ movements. Facial symmetry was maintained with competent lip. On inspection, a single diffuse swelling measuring approximately $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ was present in the chin region, extending superoinferiorly from the margin of the lower lip to the lower border of the mandible and mesiodistally from the right to the left corner of the mouth, with smooth overlying skin and obliteration of the mentolabial sulcus. On palpation, the swelling was hard, non-tender, non-compressible, and non-fluctuant, with no local rise in temperature, egg-shell crackling, sinus tract, or pus discharge.

On intraoral examination, all permanent teeth were present except 42, with an overretained 82. Pathological migration and displacement were noted with respect to 31, 32, 33, 41, and 82. Grade I mobility was present in 31, 32, 33, 41, and 43, while 82 showed Grade II mobility. A diffuse swelling measuring approximately $2 \times 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ was present in the lower labial vestibule extending from 33 to 43, with obliteration of the vestibule, and a smaller swelling $0.5 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ was noted in the lingual vestibule in relation to 41, 82, and 43. The overlying mucosa was pink and smooth. **[Figure 1]** On palpation, the swelling was hard, non-tender, non-fluctuant, non-compressible, and fixed to underlying structures. Vitality testing showed a slightly delayed response in 31, 32, and 41.

Fig. 1 : Intraoral photographs. A- Diffuse swelling is present in lower labial vestibule, B – Lingual side of swelling.

Orthopantomogram (OPG) and lateral cephalogram revealed a well-defined corticated radiolucency measuring approximately $3 \times 2 \text{ cm}$ in the anterior mandible involving teeth 31, 32, 33, 41, 43, and 82. The lesion extended from the middle third of the roots to the inferior border of the mandible, with pathological migration of the involved teeth and an impacted 42 noted at the midline lower border. CBCT sections revealed expansion of the buccal and lingual cortical plates with perforation of the lingual cortex in the midline, along with multiple radiopaque flecks within the lesion, particularly along the inferior and distal borders **[Figure 2]**

Fig. 2 : A- Lateral cephalogram of the patient. B, C, D – Coronal, Axial and Sagittal section of CBCT showing well-defined corticated radiolucency in the anterior mandible with impacted 42.

Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) was performed from the most prominent part of the swelling in the lower labial vestibule, yielding yellow straw-coloured fluid. Cytological smears revealed epithelial cells with hyperchromatic nuclei resembling odontogenic origin admixed with inflammatory cells in a serosanguinous background

Based on the clinical and radiographic findings, a provisional differential diagnosis of dentigerous cyst, Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor (AOT), Calcifying Epithelial Odontogenic Tumor (CEOT), and unicystic ameloblastoma was considered. Root Canal Treatment of the involved teeth was performed prior to surgery. Subsequently, the lesion was surgically enucleated, and the excised specimen was submitted for histopathological examination to establish a definitive diagnosis.

Gross examination of the specimen revealed a single round soft-tissue mass measuring approximately $3 \times 3 \times 2 \text{ cm}^3$, attached to a tooth. The specimen was greyish-brown in colour, firm in consistency after fixation, and exhibited a smooth external surface. [Figure 3]

Fig. 3 : Gross pathology of the Specimen

Histopathological examination revealed a cystic cavity lined by non-keratinized odontogenic epithelium resembling reduced enamel epithelium, approximately 2–3 cell layers thick, suggestive of a dentigerous cyst. **[Figure 4]** The epithelial lining showed luminal proliferations in the form of solid sheets composed of spindle, cuboidal, and columnar cells, arranged in nests, rosette-like structures, and whorls. Calcifications of varying forms were observed within the lumen. Additionally, few duct-like structures with lumina of variable size lined by a single layer of columnar epithelium were present. The underlying connective tissue stroma exhibited collagen fibres, fibroblasts, dilated blood vessels, mild chronic inflammatory cell infiltrate, and focal islands of odontogenic epithelium. Based on these findings the final diagnosis was given as dentigerous cyst converting into Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor (AOT). **[Figure 5]**

Fig. 4 : H & E stain photomicrograph under 10X and 45X shows cystic cavity lined by non-keratinized odontogenic epithelium resembling reduced enamel epithelium, approximately 2–3 cell layers thick.

Fig. 5 : H & E stain photomicrograph shows (A) Focal areas of luminal proliferation, 10X (B) Spindle shaped odontogenic epithelial cells arranged in a rosette pattern, 45X (C) Ductal structures composed of a circular arrangement of columnar cell, 45X (D) Calcification, 45X.

III.DISCUSSION

Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor is one of the most intriguing odontogenic lesions, which has been regarded as a hamartoma, a benign neoplasm, a developmental anomaly, or a cyst. [6] It is a slow-growing lesion usually occurring in the anterior maxilla and rarely reported in the mandible, and it causes a painless expansion of the jaws. It has a tendency to affect the deciduous tooth-bearing areas of the mandible and the maxilla. It has a predilection for young female patients, with a female-to-male incidence ratio of 1.9:1 and an age range of 3-82 years, 90% being diagnosed before the age of 30 years. [7,8]

The pathogenesis behind AOT still remains a subject of speculations. Some authors have mentioned that its origin is from the odontogenic cysts especially DC and have even suggested the term “hybrid variant” for AOT arising from these cysts. [9,10] On the other hand, few researchers have believed that it could be derived from fully formed enamel organ, dental lamina system complex, and/or its epithelial remnants. AOT grows into a nearby or next to a dental follicle while forming a cystic space as proposed by the “envelopmental” theory. [11] The present case fulfilled both the envelopmental pathogenesis and the “hybrid variant” concept.

The AOT has been believed to be a hamartoma rather than a neoplasm. The lesion may rarely exhibit aggressive behaviour. Radiological findings of AOTs are nonspecific and share characteristics with other odontogenic lesions, such as a dentigerous cyst, calcifying odontogenic cyst, ameloblastoma, or keratocystic odontogenic tumor. [8]

Philipsen et al. (1999) [12], categorized AOT into three variants (follicular, extrafollicular, and peripheral). The ‘follicular type’ has a central lesion associated with an impacted tooth and is the most common type accounting for 73% of cases. The ‘extrafollicular type’ has a central lesion and is not associated with the tooth, accounts for 24% of cases. The ‘peripheral type’ contributes to 4.4% of cases and is extraosseous in origin. The follicular variant of AOT is usually clinically misdiagnosed as DC. Radiographically, the pericoronal radiolucency of a dentigerous cyst occurs most frequently in the jaws,

and does not extend over the cement-enamel-junction of the tooth. However, an AOT often envelops the crown as well as the root past the cemento-enamel-junction, which distinguishes AOTs from dentigerous cysts. AOTs have numerous, variable shaped radiopaque foci, which also distinguish them from dentigerous cysts. [13] Cut surface of the AOT gross specimen shows a solid mass or a partly cystic space in contrast to cystic space of DC. In this case, aspiration revealed straw coloured fluid thinking in the way of DC, on gross examination the soft tissue showed both the solid and cystic areas which made us to consider a hybrid variant. DC is an odontogenic cyst develops by expansion of follicle in an unerupted tooth. Benign odontogenic epithelial neoplasms like ameloblastoma [14], AOT [1,8,9] and malignant neoplasms like mucoepidermoid carcinoma [15] can arise from the epithelial lining of DC. Present case is of particular interest as AOT is found in association with the fibrous capsule of DC and such hybrid variant was not discussed in the previous classifications.

Microscopically, the DC displays a thin fibrous cyst wall with a myxomatous appearance. The epithelial lining consists of 2–4 layers of flat or cuboidal cells, which in fact is the reduced enamel epithelium and is characteristically nonkeratinized. Nests, islands, or strands of odontogenic epithelium are often seen in the fibrous capsule. Localized proliferation of epithelial lining may occur in response to inflammation. Hyaline (Rushton) bodies may be found in the epithelium, especially in cysts exhibiting inflammation. Sometimes mucous secreting cells and rarely ciliated cells form a part of the epithelial lining, and occasionally sebaceous cells and lymphoid follicles with germinal centres are seen in the connective tissue. [16]

For AOT, varied histoarchitectural patterns have been documented and the WHO has defined AOT as "a tumor of odontogenic epithelium with duct-like structures and with varying degrees of inductive change in the connective tissue. The tumor may be partly cystic, and in some cases, the solid lesion may be present only as masses in the wall of a large cyst". [6,17] Histologically, the tumor consisted of a fibrous wall lined by squamous epithelium with few cell layers, as well as nodules of polyhedral cells amid small tubules of short columnar cells containing eosinophilic and mineralized material. These findings were consistent with other studies done by **John B J at al, (2010)** [18] and **Morelli H D at al (2013)** [19] which demonstrate that AOT may originate from the cystic epithelium and protrude toward the lumen.

According to the pertinent world literature, there are only a handful of AOT cases which have been reported in association with DC, especially with mandibular lateral incisor till date [Table I]. In the present case, a 17-year-old female with anterior mandibular swelling associated with an impacted lateral incisor (42). Although the lesion radiographically mimicked a dentigerous cyst, histopathology revealed a dentigerous cyst lining with focal transformation into adenomatoid odontogenic tumor, showing rosette-like structures, duct-like formations, and calcifications. This uncommon presentation in the mandibular lateral incisor region underscores the need for routine histopathological examination of all pericoronal lesions.

Case	Year	First author	Age	Sex	Site	Associated tooth
1	2011	Moosvi Z [20]	13	Female	Mandible	32
2	2015	Seo WG [13]	11	Female	Mandible	42
3	2024	Badal S [1]	16	Female	Mandible	32
4	2025	Patel S [21]	14	Female	Mandible	32

Table I: Literature review of Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor cases associated with Dentigerous Cyst, especially with mandibular lateral incisor.

The treatment of choice in such a case is conservative surgical enucleation or curettage, as both the AOT and DC are benign, encapsulated lesions and have a very less recurrence rate. More invasive treatment, such as partial block resection, should be indicated only in exceptional cases of large tumors or when there is a risk of bone fracture. Marsupialization of AOT lesions associated with DC is another option, which permits preservation of the teeth involved, followed by orthodontic repositioning. The prognosis of such cases is quite favourable, however, a long-term regular follow-up is mandatory as it is both interesting and difficult to comment upon the aggressive behaviour of the AOT, although the oncogenic potential of DC is well-documented in the literature. [22]

The AOT phenotype is characterized by cytokeratin staining immunohistochemically. According to **Larsson et al. (2003)** [23], AOT shows positive staining for CK5, CK17, and CK19, and shows negative staining for CK4, CK10, CK13, and CK18. **Crivelini et al. (2003)** [24] found CK14 in AOT and suggested that its origin was from reduced dental epithelium.

IV. CONCLUSION

This case illustrates a rare focal transformation of a dentigerous cyst into adenomatoid odontogenic tumor associated with an impacted mandibular lateral incisor in a 17-year-old female. Although the lesion closely mimicked a dentigerous cyst clinically and radiographically, histopathological examination revealed characteristic AOT features arising within the cyst lining. Such hybrid lesions in this uncommon site underscore the diagnostic pitfalls of pericoronal radiolucency and reinforce the critical importance of routine histopathological evaluation of all enucleated specimens.

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